

THE IMPACT OF HUMAN RESOURCES INFORMATION SYSTEMS ON PIVOTAL CAPACITY IN HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT POLICIES

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Abstract

Owing in information technology, the face of the contemporary workplace has changed and systems have been made more effective by introducing new techniques. Majority of the organizations have now understood the importance of information storage and retrieval. In this paper, we focus on how modern technology is helping in ensuring effectiveness of HR functions. Human Resource Information System (HRIS) is an opportunity for organizations to make the HR department administratively and strategically participative in operating the organization. The main objective is to The Impact of Human Resources Information Systems on Pivotal Capacity in Human Resources Management policies for this purpose, we have conducted a survey of 150 HR employees from Amazon Foundation. The results show that Human Resources Information Systems is positively used as a tool to Pivotal Capacity in Human Resources Management policies.

Keywords: Human Resources Information Systems, Pivotal Capacity in Human Resources Management policies

Introduction

The most important characteristic of the changes and the vast shifts in the atheist and the twentieth century is the development of global management thought, to look at the human element as a mere labor is at the beginning of the twentieth century to the attention of human minds as knowledge and creativity source, which represents the fulcrum of any developmental work and was one of the areas of work within organizations, which needed a comprehensive change and adapt - the field for human resources management, it was not possible to continue the role of "people management" as they were called before the year (1980 as substituted major universities in this Mil named HRM) Human Resource Management), and did not change is limited to named only, but extended the change to content, roles, too, became a human resources management of their own strategy, fused in the overall strategy of the organization, and is an integral part of them, as well as integration and Tnsagaha with, since the human resources management strategy plays an important role in achieving the overall strategic objectives Delorme and Arcand, 2015).

Human resources strategy that focuses on the proper use of the Organization of the human resources to assist them in maintaining or improving their competitiveness in the labor market. Modern studies look at the human resources management strategy as one of the central components of the strategy for the business organization at a time when those strategies is relatively non-a was important from the viewpoint of senior management, as it has not seen in

the best of cases more than one point of access to the activities and acts of office documentary dealing with workers and their affairs.

The big developments in the private business environment technological ones did not let human resources management live in palaces that view circle. The atheist and the onset of the twentieth century increasingly confessions emerged that the path towards achieving competitive advantage will be achieved through actual workers, the business organization based on human resources in building strategies reflect the existence of an effective means for workers first and before the existence of the strategy Hendrickson R. Anthony (2013).

In this study, the researchers studied the impact of human resources information systems in the pivotal competencies in human resources management policies applied study on Jordanian commercial banks. In light of these changes, which is a clear challenge for organizations in Jordan, and by linking the concepts of this study, the researchers have identified the problem of the study

The theoretical background of the study

Conducted (Sakka, 2016) study aimed to describe the reality of the use of human-mail resources information system in the office of public the workers in the Gaza Strip, and the impact of this use on the performance of the Bureau of the four aspects of the Sub: (effectiveness, efficiency, and quality of performance, and the time required for the performance), of viewpoint staff who use this system. The study results showed that a user electronic human resources information system already use and has led to improved performance of the Bureau through its contribution to increase the effectiveness, efficiency and quality performance. And also study by (Roshan and Alomosh, 2013) this study aimed to identify the performance of human resources information system in the organizational loyalty. The study results showed the presence of a statistically significant relationship between the impact of human resources information system and between loyalty, and there is no trace of human resources planning. and study (Al-Mobaideen et al, 2018) aims to describe the impact of human resources information systems to identify training needs, set goals of training programs and their implementation, and evaluation and follow-up training in industrial enterprises effective in the city of Aqaba. The study results showed that there is a link between the human resources information systems and the training needs, it identifies the objectives of the training programs, and showed the extent of the implementation of these training programs in the evaluation and follow-up in industrial establishments in the city of Aqaba. and Conducted (Gulati & Khera, 2012) study aimed to identify the benefits of human resources information systems in the information technology organizations, and to clarify the role of human resources systems in strategic activities for human resource managers in human resource planning in these organizations, the study concluded that the results of the most important information resources systems human help: take the same high efficiency of HR decisions. Provide supervision and control best workforce in the organization. and in study conducted by (Obeidat, 2018) aimed to discuss linking human resources information and functions of human resource management systems, based on the theoretical framework for the study of the former Human Resources and Research Department, where he was to measure the role of the

contribution of human resources by compliance and the level of application of HR functions. The study results showed that the strategic integration, forecasting, planning and analysis of human resources, communications, and integration does not have anything to do with jobs. While showing that the development of performance and knowledge management and records, have to do with the functions of Human Resources, one of the dimensions of human resources information system. and Conducted Miloud ,2010) study aimed to clarify the role of human resources information systems in the performance of human resource assessment, the study found that the human resources information systems in the organization always need to be developed so that it can achieve the assumed it performed tasks, and makes the process of human resources performance evaluation more effective. According to the researchers set of recommendations, including: subjecting workers in human resources management training courses to enable them to face and cope with technological changes and use them to perform their duties. And the study. (Abu Rahma, 2015), which aimed to recognize the extent of the efficiency of human resources information systems in the ministries of the Palestinian National Authority in the Gaza Strip, and the most important factors that limit their efficiency, and their impact on the effectiveness of personnel management, and provide some suggestions that can contribute to improving the efficiency of human resources information systems, so that they can play their role in the provision of appropriate information on which they depend personnel management in decision-making, to carry out its responsibilities efficiently and effectively, and the study results showed that the availability of human resources used information Systems the employee at high rates of accuracy for most of the elements of information. He (Stone et al, 2006) study aimed to identify factors influencing the acceptance of the efficiency of e -HR systems, and their impact on human resource functions. The study found that, although the e-HR systems may be effective in both the organization and the individuals, they may be the reason to disable some functions of organizations and individuals, such as human relations and privacy. The study recommended the reduction and control of electronic media and supervision that restrict the freedom of individuals, and the use of a combination of traditional and electronic systems and good and proper design of the system to help increase efficiency. and Conducted study (Cronin et al, 2005) aimed to determine the effectiveness of the application of modern technology within human resources department, and problems resulting from its application, and it turns out that there are effective application of technology in human resources management in terms of reducing anxiety levels when working and that there is a high productivity, as shown that the introduction of technology in business organizations contribute to increased credibility and reliability in their own human resources management decision-making.

The problem and question of the study

Recently increased awareness of organizations of the importance and effectiveness of human resources as a factor in business success, both at the individual level or the company level or at the economic level as a whole, since it represented an important resource of organizations, and the most important assets that cannot achieve the objectives of the organization without human resources so the organization should strive for attention of it . Many organizations aim to develop the skills and competencies of its human resources to be able to achieve the

organization's goals effectively and efficiently and to help in the face of external and internal changes and challenges. And because the increase in the size and complexity of organizations and administrative activities, and the development of types of decision-making led to increased interest of managers at different organizational and functional levels to get accurate and appropriate information in the appropriate time. Therefore, information systems has become the most important resources of the organizations, but many organizations are still Suffer from the understanding of the importance of human resource information system and its importance in achieving the organization's objectives.

According to the previously mentioned study can show the problem more clearly through the following key question: “The Impact of Human Resources Information Systems on Pivotal Capacity on Human Resources Management policies.

Objectives of the study:

This study seeks to achieve the following objectives:

1. Identify the impact of human resources information systems in the pivotal Capacity on human resources management policies.
2. Identify the level of importance of human resources information systems, according to the perceptions of respondents.
3. Identify the level of the pivotal importance of Capacity on human resources management policies, according to the dimensions of the respondents' perceptions.
4. To make recommendations that will help to maximize the interest of human resources information systems in pivotal in human resources management policies Capacity.

The Importance of the study

The importance of this study comes from the growing interest in the human resources information and topics of human resources in general systems, the importance of this study determine through the following points:

- 1- Identify the impact of human resources information systems in the pivotal Capacity in human resources management policies, which represents the subject of a high degree of importance to decision-makers, politicians, researchers and the public to provide and help them in their purposes service.
- 2- The newness of the subject of human resources information systems, especially Arab ones and the lack of studies and research.
- 3- This study also derives its importance from the results that will be useful to researchers and those interested in this field to get information and statistics in the field of human resources

Hypotheses of the study

Based on previous studies, the researchers formulate null hypothesis that measure the variables of the study, and to draw conclusions and recommendations, which are as follows:

The main Hypothesis: There is no significant impact statistically significant systems and human resources information dimensions (the efficiency of human resources information systems, integration with other sub-management information systems, response) in competencies pivotal in human resources management policies dimensions (deserved problem solving, technical merit, merit cognitive) at the significance level (0.05).

The Study Model

Research Design

For an effective research, it is imperative to select an appropriate research methodology. An appropriate research design is important to determine the type of data needed, method of collecting the data, and type of sampling technique to apply. Therefore, research design is very crucial to actualize the research objectives (Bhatti, Hee, & Sundram, 2012). This study applied a quantitative research design. Quantitative research design will enable the researcher to test the relationship between the research variables (Bhatti, Hee, & Sundram, 2012). It will also enable the researcher to unvaryingly determine if one concept or idea is better than the others (Sekaran & Bougie, 2013). It can also respond to questions on the relationships that exist among measured variables with the aim of elucidating, envisaging, as well as controlling phenomena (Sekaran & Bougie, 2010).

Thus, quantitative research design is an appropriate method for this study since it permits testing the relationship between variables with the use of statistical approaches (Sekaran & Bougie, 2013). This is in line with the main objective of this study that focus The Impact of Human Resources Information Systems on Pivotal Capacity in Human Resources Management policies

Population and Sample of the Study

The study population was limited to in Amazon Foundation and the individuals who participated in the study to answer a tool to understand all the departments of human resources and staff numbered 150 employees.

Determine the sample size of the study in the light of the two types of considerations: first, technical considerations include the degree of homogeneity of society (Homogonous) any study population and the proportion of errors that can be tolerated by the researcher, and the second: a non-systematic considerations (time to collect data and material resources and general considerations), and specialists scientific research realize that the general rule in the selection of the relatively small community needs to be larger sample until all the special vocabulary represents If this community is not homogeneous.

The Study Tool:

Use the researchers (questionnaire) as a tool to collect data from the sample elements to cover the field side in this study due to its questionnaire of saving time and effort in all the data of the study population, especially since this study is applied in (Amazon Foundation) and allow resolution images of the components of the sample show scientific and professional opinions and suggestions in order to achieve the objectives of the present study.

Statistical Analysis

The use of statistical packages for Social Sciences (SPSS.16.1) (The Statistical Package of Social Sciences) in data processing to answer questions about the study and testing of hypotheses.

DATA RELIABILITY

In this study, we used Chronbach's alpha Table (1) and it is the most common test for data reliability. It is a measure of how well each variable in a scale correlates with the sum of the remaining variables. Thus, the current study used this method to measure data reliability. The data of the current research was accumulating statistically from reports and studies. For the purpose of data analysis, several statistical techniques are apply, descriptive statistics, factor analysis, correlation analysis, and Multiple Regression analysis.

Table 1

Cronbach's alpha	Number of Paragraphs	Domain
%90	3	The efficiency of human resources Information systems
%87	3	Integration with other systems
%92	3	Response

For answering the first question states: what is the impact of The Impact of Human Resources Information Systems on Pivotal Capacity in Human Resources Management policies? Linear regression was found f table (3) clarifies that:

Data Analysis:

To answer the questions of the study, the accumulated data have to be analyzed by using the Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS Version (15.0). the researcher also used

the following statistic methods: means, standard deviation, and percentages as well as the Pearson correlation coefficient.

Linear regression of the domain which measures The Impact of Human Resources Information Systems on Pivotal Capacity in Human Resources Management policies?

Table 2

significance level	B Value	Sum of Square	R Square	R value	Domain
.005	1.156	14.835	.239	.366 ^a	The efficiency of human resources Information systems
.005	.986	22.980	.230	.479 ^a	Integration with other systems
.000	1.198	25.766	.380	.616 ^a	Response

Table (2) shows there are statically significance differences for The Impact of Human Resources Information Systems on Pivotal Capacity in Human Resources Management policies, value (005.) The efficiency of human resources Information systems domain value statically significance at the level (005.) And beta value was (1.156) And **R Square** value was (.239) which shows level of impact of The efficiency of human resources Information systems on Pivotal Capacity in Human Resources Management policies and Integration with other systems statically significance level (005.) its value statically significance at the level (005.) And beta value was (986.) And **R Square** value was .230) which shows impact level of Integration with other systems on Pivotal Capacity in Human Resources Management policies. In addition to Response domain significance value (000.) with value statically significance at the level (005.)And beta value was (1.198) and **R Square** value was (.380) which shows impact level of Response on Pivotal Capacity in Human Resources Management policies.

Conclusions

In light of data analysis, the discussion of the study assumptions, the most important results reached through the present study can be summarized as follows;

The first conclusion; The Impact of Human Resources Information Systems on Pivotal Capacity in Human Resources Management policies.

The second conclusion; impact level of Integration with other systems on Pivotal Capacity in Human Resources Management policies impact of The efficiency of human resources Information systems on Pivotal Capacity in Human Resources Management policies

The third conclusion; impact level of Integration with other systems on Pivotal Capacity in Human Resources Management policies. And the impact level of Response on Pivotal Capacity in Human Resources Management policies.

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